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Vocational Students at Risk of Social Exclusion in Estonia: Social Ecology Approach

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Abstract

The study focuses on the social ecology of learning and development of students at risk of drop out from IVET that could lead to early school leaving and social exclusion. To understand better the complex of the interrelated factors of drop out risks the concepts of social ecology, ecological agency form the theoretical and methodological framework of the study. Sample of interviewed students consists of 20 students (14 female and 6 male) of age between 16 and 22 years from different vocational schools and regions in Estonia studying different specialities. Among sample there are students who had dropped out from several schools as well as those that have had rather smooth educational careers. As the result of empirical analysis, we identified three clusters of students, representing three different ecologies of students at risk with the emphasis on the development of their agentic capacities. The ecologies reflect also different experiences of getting help or not in the close environments of students in the case of emerging problems and the consequences on their further learning and development, including the perspectives for the future life.

Keywords

social ecology, students at risk, vocational education

1 Introduction

The focus of the study is on the social ecology of learning and development of students in the situation of risk of dropping out from IVET (initial vocational education) that could lead to early school leaving and social exclusion. Tackling social exclusion and supporting at-risk groups has been a high priority in the European Union (EU) policies during the last decade and more. Although the early leaving rate from education and training has steadily decreased from

13.8% in 2010 to 9.7% in 2021, progress has stagnated since 2016 with significant differences across countries, regions, genders and for specific population groups (Psifidou et al., 2022). Despite policy interventions the share of vocational students, who interrupt studies and share of dropouts in Estonia has remained almost the same, accordingly 20% and 12% over the years (Jaggo, 2019). The same problem can be identified also in some other EU countries, particularly those, having school-based VET systems (Psifidou et al., 2022). Previous studies reveal that the main causes of social exclusion among young people are low motivation, negative learning and life experiences, low skill levels, no future prospects or unrealistic future expectations (Goldman-Mellor et al., 2016; Ose & Jensen, 2017; Beck, 2015). In 2013-2017, the most common reasons for dropping out of vocational education in Estonia were failure to study, absence from studies, employment or economic reasons, vocation unsuitability, health and other reasons (Jaggo, 2019, p.20). The problem of social exclusion is challenging because of its complexity, i.e. involvement of various factors and multilevel institutional and individual actors. Unfortunate circumstances and situations can create the self-sustaining vicious circle of exclusion in early age that may cause cumulative educational disadvantages that are impossible to break out without external help (Reiska, 2018). Therefore, it is highly important to understand better the reasons for dropping out in the wider social and personal context and provide systematic and individualized support.

We approach the problem of students in the drop-out risk from IVET from socio-ecological perspective to better understand the complex of impacting factors and the ways how the social ecology of their learning and development functions. The social ecological approach also allows to look at the risk factors that have been mainly described in individual terms (low academic results, motivation problems etc) as related to broader structural and institutional factors and give more holistic understanding of the processes and mechanisms contributing to the becoming into the risk (Lörnic, D'Angelo & Kaye, 2019, p. 413).

2 The institutional and structural context

At the macro level, the potential institutions that play a role in the ecology of students at risk, concern the mutual relationships between general and vocational education and labour market. IVET in Estonia is provided after the 9-year basic, compulsory education at the lower and upper secondary level. The latter means that students get in parallel to a vocational certificate also certificate of general upper secondary education that allows them to continue studies at Higher Education (HE) level. IVET is provided also at the level of lower secondary education (students get vocational, but not secondary education certificate) that doesn't allow them to continue studies at HE level. Estonian vocational education system can be characterized as a school-based system with rather strong segregation at secondary level (Loogma, 2022). Students with lower academic results and/or vulnerable family/socio-economic family background tend to move after basic education to the vocational track and academically more capable to the general secondary education track. The negative selection to the IVET track is based on the historically determined and socially shared beliefs about the VET's inferiority of vocational education as to compare to academic education (Loogma et al., 2019). The negative selection into the IVET track has been reproduced by a vicious cycle involving social and cultural mechanisms, such as feedback from labour market and employers (e.g. lower salaries of graduates of IVET, feedback from employers about poor general skills of IVET graduates, modest ability for movements in labour market and education etc) keeps this ecology to "work". Therefore, in addition to the historically evolved understandings about the "inferiority" of IVET, interactions between those beliefs and actual labour market outcomes work as the main mechanisms of sustainability of this pattern at macro level. (*Ibid*).

3 Conceptual framework and research questions

Social ecology approach

Social ecology is treated not as the established and consistent theory, but rather as a methodological approach to analyse complex phenomena (e.g. Weaver-Hightower, 2008; Evans et al., 2011) The two main analytical directions can be distinguished in the applications of social ecological analysis. The Bronfenbrenner's well-known ecological system theory (1979) has an individual as primary unit of analysis focussing on the development of an individual in the framework of interdependencies in and between five-level (both, closer and distant) environments that shape young peoples' opportunities and experiences (Lörnic et al., 2019). The another cluster of applications of socio-ecological approach is related rather to the macro-level analysis, analysis of organizations and various social groups (Evans et al., 2011, p. 356) and as well, policy analysis (Weaver-Hightower, 2008). Both directions share the idea of dynamic and multilevel interdependencies enabling an ecology to work and self-sustain. However, several different conceptual frameworks for application of this interdisciplinary analysis have utilized as the aims and contexts of phenomena studied varies widely. Social ecology approach has been applied for research across the different areas and for different phenomena in many contexts (Jackson & Barnett, 2020), including a number of studies, conducted specifically to better understand learning and development in various contexts and uncover factors, that impact directly or indirectly the learning and development in certain practices. (*Ibid*).

Generally, by a social ecology we understand the social associations that function in the interplay of multilevel structures, institutions, individual actors and their interrelations, and interactions. Thus, political processes, historical-cultural circumstances, power relations, socio-economic changes, social relationships can form self-regulating and self-sustaining ecologies (Weaver-Hightower, 2008; Evans, 2020). The analysis of any social ecology can include following categories of elements of an ecology: involved actors and their relationships, environments, structures /institutions, processes and changes that allow the process and ecology to work (Weaver-Hightower, 2008, p. 156). Education and labour market institutions, families, friends and other actors and institutions interact in the generation of learning ecologies that can be experienced as transformative, adaptive or reproductive of social inequalities (Evans, 2020, p.164). Because of self-organizational dynamics that function without the central control/regulation individuals and groups have possibilities to exercise *agency* and therefore influence the all dynamics of an ecology through the interdependences. (Weaver-Hightower, 2008). The understanding of human development as contextualized by Bronfenbrenner's ecological system theory coincides with the contextualized understanding of agency that makes concept of agency significant for social ecological analysis.

Ecological agency

According the conceptualization of ecological agency (Emirbayer & Mische, 1998; Biesta & Tedder, 2007), agency is treated not as an individual capacity, rather as bounded to a context, something that people do and that has to be achieved in and through engagement with particular environment (contexts-for-action). The approach of ecological agency also suggests that agency should be understood as a process, that is a composition of influences from the *past experience*, orientations towards the *future* and quality of engagement with the *present*. (Biesta & Tedder, 2007, p.135). Ecological agency emphasizes on the changing interdependences between the context and personal conditions in development of agency while a person moves from one environment to another (Emirbayer & Mische, 1998). In this process actors "recompose" their temporal-relational orientations (agentic orientations) and are capable of changing their relationship to structure (*Ibid*, p. 1006). The concept focuses on the ways in which agency is achieved in a particular context-for-action, within a particular 'ecology'. (*Ibid*).

Treating agency as achieved does also mean that the agentic capabilities, such as self-confidence, self-regulation, goal-determination and others can develop and should be supported in an environment to meet challenges and overcome them.

The framework for ecological analysis of learning and development of students at risk in IVET
For the analysis of students' experience we apply the adopted triangle model of Eraut (2004, p.269) and Evans et al. (2011, p.360) of mutual relationships between:

- challenges, students meet in various (institutional) environments;
- support and feedback, they may get/or not to meet challenges and overcome difficulties in a specific context
- (impact on) the development of agentic capacities, such as (self)confidence, motivation, purposiveness, perseverance, initiative and others.

The model is related to the view of ecological agency, involving development of agentic orientations (Emirbayer & Mische, 1998, p.1004) that may change while students move between different environments such as between different schools, from school to work etc. and where they meet challenges that require learning and are considered as difficulties encountered in a specific context. The ways of overcoming the difficulties may result in growth of agentic capacities that in turn, have potential to transform the at-risk situation and open up for students the ways to move on in education and/or work and not be excluded. At the same time, lack of support and/or unmet encountered difficulties may result in reproduction and continuation of the at risk situation in other contexts in the future. We presume, that capacity or ability to meet challenges depends on how students are supported whether by the family members, teachers, peers or whether a student feel to be supported.

The aim of the paper is to better understand the process of learning and development of young IVET students at risk from the viewpoint of social ecology and understand the impacting factors of the risk situation from the perspective of young people themselves, based on their experience in the different micro level / close environments.

The research focuses on the questions: 1) how the students at risk perceive the roles (e.g. supportive or restricting) and interrelationships of actors in the process of their learning and development? 2) What kind of social mechanisms (e.g. interrelated factors and interdependencies) can be identified in the social ecology of students at risk allowing to transform or reproduce the inclusion/exclusion?

4 Methodology

Sample of interviewed students includes young people in IVET who are at risk of dropping-out from VET school. The sample consists of 20 students (14 female and 6 male) of age range between 16 and 22 years. Students were from 6 different vocational schools in Estonia studying different specialities. Among sample there are students who had dropped out from several schools as well as those that have had rather smooth educational careers. Students are from different regions and with different social and family backgrounds. The data were collected by the semi-structured individual interviews that involved sections, covering students' family background, past and present school and work experiences, social activity, support and future plans. Interviews were mediated via Zoom web-environment extending between 50 and 60 minutes, recorded by Zoom recording system and transcribed verbatim. The ethical principles of informed consent, confidentiality, and the responsibility for data processing in accordance with data protection legislation were followed in the research. The plan for research ethics was improved by the ethical board of research at Tallinn University.

While analysing transcribed texts we combined deductive analysis with narrative analysis. First, we analysed text, based on the triangle model, starting from the identifying main challenges and problems students encounter in the different learning environments they are

engaged in at micro-level or close environments (family, schools, hobby circles, work (practical training as part of IVET curriculum, occasional/summertime jobs, volunteering and other work) and others. Then we analysed the process of overcoming the challenges and whether students get help. Further, we analysed the implications of the ways challenges were overcome or not on the further development of a student, particularly what concerns development of agentic abilities. Then we clustered the students' personal stories as processes of interrelations between challenges and support in particular environments with the implications on further development of students' learning and agency. Finally, we constructed short narratives that embrace individual students' background and challenging experiences over time. The portrayals are presented as characterizing different ecologies of learning and development of students.

5 Analysis of students' experience

As the result of empirical analysis, we identified three clusters of students, representing three different ecologies of learning and development of at-risk students with the emphasis on the development of their agentic capacities. The ecologies reflect also different experiences of getting help or not in school(s) in the case of emerging problems and the consequences on their further learning and development, including the visions/perspectives for the future life.

First, some students are convinced and confident they can solve the challenges and problems they encounter at school and work themselves and they don't need any help (from teachers nor from schools). However, they still have supportive relationships outside the school to rely on. It seems to happen in these cases when students are interested, motivated and goal-determined in their studies and future (career) prospects. **Rain's** story can be interpreted as a case of transformative ecology as it refers to the rise of agentic capacities and at the same time, favourable prospects for future. Rain is an example of the type of students who exercise agency making purposeful choices while choosing IVET and have rather clear vision for his future work. Rain studied cooking in a vocational school after basic school, which is his purposeful choice. In the basic school he had difficulties with math. He characterizes teachers as angry and rigid, labelling students. Math teacher put him in the low performance group. Even if he had courage to ask for help, he didn't get help and felt that the teacher liked to help well-performing students much more. „... *help [from teachers] was varying ... for example, some teachers try to show how [to do correctly]; another teacher however, try to show quickly to move on to her favourite students*“. Despite this negative experience he succeeded to finish basic school to move on to vocational school to study cooking he liked and was interested in. Another challenge he met in the course of practical training in a restaurant. At the beginning work was very difficult; however he is proud that coped finally well *...there were small rooms, ... the meal was very complicated (many components)...however, four weeks was enough to make things clear for myself ...I learned to perform everything well*. Besides cooking he is very interested in military activities (as a hobby) taking steadily part of military trainings with his brothers. He has few friends, however considers relationships with brothers and training mates as close ones. In meeting those challenges he is finally convinced that can cope well even without external help by learning by himself *“I can cope by myself and doesn't need external help“*

Secondly, another type of ecology refers rather to adaptive type of ecology. **Meelis's** story demonstrates the case when the basic school environment was felt as restrictive and isolating, vocational school on the contrary, was experienced as rather positive and supportive, raising self-confidence and well-being. Even though he overcame trauma experienced at basic school, and argues that will finish the school, he still feels that cannot change things around him and hesitates to pose more ambitious goals for the future arguing that he is lazy, trying to cope with as little efforts as possible and is afraid of failing at work. Meelis was bullied in the basic school that lasted from 4th grade to 8th grade. Even teachers tried to handle the problem and mother supported when he didn't want to go to school anymore the bullying eventually stopped and he

was recognised by others while he started regularly taking up sport - exercising the lifting. Even he found the way to avoid bullying he was upset „*That's I didn't like that I was accepted by others only when I started to exercise* “. As well, he has difficulties with math. However, he feels himself much successful and confident at vocational school as the marks are better and importantly, he gets positive feedback from teachers. He has challenges in vocational school in math at the beginning; however, he overcome them and suddenly become the best in the class in math and earned positive feedback from teachers,, ... *I am doing well in math; teacher prizes me... and... in speciality lessons I am doing well, teacher asked to help him* “.

The *third* type of ecology demonstrate how an ecology may work to reproduce exclusion. **Heli** studies in a vocational school 2nd year as construction finisher. Even though she chose construction finisher field rather coincidentally (schoolmates study this and her father is working in the field) she likes the field. She has some friends outside of school and rather good family relationships. In the primary school she experienced a lot of school bullying. Later, in the 5th grade she moved to a small school in the countryside where she experienced very good relationships recalling the school as *very cool* even though she had to repeat a class once. She was rather active at this school, and was also a member of the student union at the basic school. After the basic school she has left two vocational schools because of conflicts with teachers and her *laziness* studying currently in the third one. She has complicated relationships with some of teachers and as well, with her group mates currently. She gets a feeling that she doesn't have enough energy and motivation to do all the tasks at school and thinks to leave the school again to go to work. Even though she gets support from a teacher and her brother, she feels, that is lazy and not good at dealing with (time) pressure and therefore, she knows that *it is better to start fresh*. She is rather confused about her future perspectives.

6 Conclusions

The results indicate that the life and learning paths of young people at risk are influenced by micro-level actors, such as family members, teachers and peers, in the basic school that precede vocational school. The environment for emerge and support of agentic capacities of students varies from context to context. Some students who experience little support at the school can have possibilities for self-expression and get support while working. The opposite cases came forward as well. Some students who feel to be supported and safe in the vocational school had difficulties and fears to go to work. Even though students feel the growth in terms of self confidence in vocational school, it does not mean, that they feel to have enough power or will to influence on the surrounding environments and they prefer to *stay in the back* and not to express her/his opinions.

Family has perceived rather as supportive even in the cases of “broken” families and/or parents working abroad. At least some family members, though distant members are supportive in school matters. The experience of students at basic school, may be affected by the family background as the choice to move to study into vocational track after the basic school was in many cases suggested by members of a family, considering also the proximity of a school to the place of living. Some students struggle with serious problems at basic school, related to the combination of bad relationships with peers (related also to school bulling) and teachers, learning difficulties and feeling of isolation and little support at school. Although having supportive family relationships, family may not be able to provide enough support. The situation can even lead to mental health problems that in turn can result in disengagement, missing lessons and learning difficulties. Feeling of disengagement and learning difficulties refer to the dissatisfaction of some of basic psychological needs (needs for relatedness and competence) that lead to amotivation (Gagne & Deci, 2005, p.337).

If the problems haven't been properly met at earlier stages of education the consequences tend to carry forward to vocational school and moreover, to the further (educational) choices

and achievements through decrease of agentic capacities of students. Another mechanism of becoming into the risk situation is related to the health problems of students. No matter whether the health problems can be caused by traumas in earlier periods of life or not, the health problems, such as anxiety, stress and others if not treated properly, can restrict the normal learning and development of students in IVET and in the later life. As well, some risks of exclusion are related to the social economic circumstances of the families of students. The need to earn own money may put pressure on students to go to work as soon as possible; this, in turn, can result of interruption of studies.

However, in some cases transition from basic school to vocational school was appreciated by students and vocational school seems to be more suitable environment for them allowing more flexibility in studies, and teachers and peers are more supportive and caring. In those cases, the vocational school may support agentic capacities of students who had negative experience at basic school mainly through the positive feedback and support in the case of leaning difficulties, creation of positive climate and paying attention to students' concerns. Positive experience at the vocational school can help to broke up the wicked-cycle of reproducing risks and possibly lead to adaptive and/or transformative ecologies of learning and development of students.

Thus, as the result of concurrency of many unfortunate circumstances, such as little support from families, poor learning results, school bullying and negative labelling by teachers at basic school the agentic capacities such as self-esteem and confidence of the young people at-risk decrease. Those situations may have long lasting consequences on students' lives, reproducing the risks and rising the likelihood for social exclusion. However, despite the pervious negative experience of students' vocational education still has possibilities to change the reproductive ecology to adaptive or transformative that would enable students to move on in more or less ambitious way.

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